

Research Article

Exploring Factors Influencing Muslim Millennial Moms' Consumer Decision-Making Process in Choosing Birthplace

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Abstract: Choosing a birthplace is a crucial decision that substantially affects the mother's well-being. In contrast to prior studies that have primarily focused on birthplace from a medical standpoint, the emergence of consumerism has caused Muslim millennial mothers to transition from being passive patients to becoming active consumers. This shift is evident in the growing number of admissions for childbirth in private hospitals and the corresponding decline in government hospitals. This study aims to investigate the factors that affect the decision-making process of Muslim millennial women while selecting their birthplace, as evaluated by consumers. Qualitative descriptive phenomenological methodology was employed to conduct in-depth interviews with six participants. The collected material was then analyzed using Collaizi's descriptive phenomenology paradigm. Two major themes emerged from the findings: individual and environmental factors. This study provides significant insights into the intricate elements that influence the birthplace choices of Muslim millennial women. This Knowledge has the potential to assist healthcare marketers and service providers in creating more focused and efficient strategies to cater to the requirements of this crucial consumer group.

Keywords: birthplace, consumer decision-making, millennial moms, belief, preferences

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1. INTRODUCTION

Birthplace decision-making is complex and crucial to women's childbirth experiences (López-Toribio et al., 2021). In some cultures, it has significant socio-cultural implications (Barbi et al., 2021). Even though women experience the same phenomenon, they decide differently (Raoust et al., 2022). Health and medical researchers' prior studies on birthplace and childbirth were extensive (i.e., Hinton et al., 2018; Coxon et al., 2017). However, extensive research is carried out through the lenses of health and medical practitioners. Disregard the consumer role and perspectives as part of the birthplace decision-making process. The advent of technology and digital communication platforms has polarized the healthcare sector tremendously, and the rise of consumerism brings inward consumer voices and participation in health (birthplace) decision-making (Temkina, 2020) to the decision process.

For that matter, health scholars have begun to incorporate the consumer decision model in comprehending health-related phenomena. For example, Komatsu et al. (2021) included the well-known consumer decision model (Engel, Blackwell & Miniard, EBM) in their study exploring psychiatric neural networks. The EBM model is one of the most comprehensive consumer decision-making models (Ewerhard et al., 2019). However, the EBM model has received some critiques from service scholars, highlighting the shortcomings of the model in comprehending the service decision-making process. The critiques are highlighted in the table below:

Table 1. Critiques of the EBM Model

Critiques	Author(s)
The sequential model can't capture the dynamic decision-making process, which frequently involves time and space-overlapping decision activities.	Faulds et al. (2018)
The model is linear and mechanistic	Gonzalvo et al. (2021)
Incorporating the complexity of consumer decision-making situations is difficult	Peter & Olson (2010)
The model's environmental and individual variables are ambiguous, making it difficult to explain and quantify their effects on the decision-making stages.	Loudon & Bitta (1993)
Incapability to describe nonconscious behavioral responses that may not be comprehensively modelled using a sensible information processing approach	Erasmus et al. (2001)

However, given that it has been accepted and adopted in health research (Komatsu et al., 2021), the researchers were enticed to investigate the birthplace decision-making process of Muslim millennial moms by utilizing the well-known and comprehensive consumer decision-making model in choosing birthplace. Thus, this study aims to explore the variables influencing Muslim millennial moms' birthplace decision-making process from the consumer's perspective. The study outcomes will benefit the industry player, service provider, and marketer in capturing and comprehending the uniqueness of the Muslim millennial mom market and tailoring the maternity service product offering strategically.

The earliest generation of the model of the consumer decision-making process was known as the grand model (Ewerhard et al., 2019). The pioneering concept of grand models was identified based on its systematic and thorough understanding of consumer buying (Sirakaya & Woodside, 2005; Kassarjian, 1982). The comprehensiveness and applicability of grand models make the models the most influential decision-making theory, and they are still practiced by researchers in understanding consumer behavior (Mehta et al., 2020). Among the well-known Grand Models are the Nicosia model, Andreason Model, Howard and Sheth buyer behavior model, and Engel, Blackwell, and Miniard (EBM) consumer decision process model (Baksi, 2020). Ewehard et al. (2020) identified that among the grand model, the most applied and commonly used decision model is the seven stages of the consumer decision process (EBM) model.

1.1 Engel, Blackwell, and Minniard (EBM) Consumer Decision-Making Process Model

The EBM model was the extension of the Engel, Kollart, and Blackwell (EKB) traditional consumer decision-making model, consisting of five decision stages (Mehta et al., 2020). The later revised EBM model extended another two stages (consumption and divestment) to comprehensively capture the consumer decision-making process (Ewerhard et al., 2020). The EBM model was

constructed into four different areas, which are (1) information input, (2) information processing, (3) decision-making process, and (4) variables that influence the decision-making process . Figure 1 below illustrates the EBM model that is referred to in this research.

Figure 1. EBM Model (Source adopted from Yousuf & Maitlo, 2019)

This research examined the variables influencing Muslim millennial moms' birthplace decisions. According to Yousuf and Maitlo (2019), the EBM model divides decision variables into two categories: environmental influences (i.e., social class, family, friends, culture, and personal influence) and individual differences. (i.e., attitudes, beliefs, Knowledge, motivation, resources, and personality). The decision variables significantly influence the decision process, which the variables can significantly influence the information process and decision process (Tang et al., 2019). An earlier study by Durmaz and Tesdemir (2014) has coined the importance of environmental influences (family, social class) and individual differences (attitude, lifestyle) significantly influencing consumer behavior and decision-making.

1.2 Variables Influencing Decision Model

The two categories of EBM decision variables are discussed in Table 2.

Table 2. EBM Decision Variables Categories

Individual Differences	Description
Knowledge	Consumer knowledge about the particular product. Informed consumers make better decisions (Karimi et al., 2015)
Attitude	How consumers react (favorable/non-favorable) to a particular product. It consists of effect, belief, and intention (Niosi, 2021)
Motivation	Motivation is crucial in decision-making. What is the motive for buying? It is an inner feeling that stimulates individual behavior and action (Levitt et al., 2019)

Personality, Values & Lifestyle	<p>Lifestyle; a person's way of life as expressed by consumer acts, preferences, and opinions.</p> <p>Personality: Personality refers to the distinctive psychological traits that distinguish a person or group of people (Qazzafi, 2020)</p> <p>Value: Values express people's goals and how they achieve them (Burton, 2022)</p>
Consumer Resources/ Economic	A consumer's economic situation influences his or her purchasing decision and selection of a particular brand or product (Qazzafi, 2020)
Environment Influences	Description
Family	Family, friends, and peers are significant decision influencers and trusted sources (Nash, 2019)
Culture	The collection of learned belief systems, value systems, and traditions that govern the behavior of members of a specific society (Niosi, 2021)
Situation	temporary situations that influence how buyers to act. External factors can influence decisions, such as atmosphere, location, layout, and time (Ali et al., 2020)
Social Class	Social class is the segment of society arrived at by a hierarchical classification of individuals and families with distinct statuses (Kraus et al., 2019)
Personal Influence	The ability of individuals to influence or exert control over other people's purchase decisions (Burton, 2022).

Despite this, little research has been conducted on the variables influencing the decision-making process. Most of the research (Ewerhard et al., 2020) focused solely on the decision process rather than the variables that may have a significant later impact on the decision process.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

In this research, qualitative descriptive phenomenology is employed. Phenomenology is a qualitative research method that focuses on acquiring an understanding of human behavior through the eyes of study participants (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). Phenomenological research permits the researcher to delve deeper into the meaning and experiences of the mothers of Muslim millennials regarding the factors that influence their consumer decision-making process when choosing their birthplace. Neubauer et al. (2019) pointed out that phenomenology is an appropriate methodology for understanding and addressing health-related decision-making because it enables the researcher to comprehend the phenomenon under investigation through the lived experiences of others.

2.1 Sampling

This research employed purposive maximum variation sampling techniques in identifying the participants. The maximum-variation sampling technique was utilized to select the participants. The primary objective of maximum variation sampling is to establish a smaller sample while maximizing

the individual types (experience) that can be related to the phenomenon being studied (Palinkas et al., 2015). This sampling technique generates comprehensive descriptions of each incident that are valuable in capturing the uniqueness and shared patterns that distinguish experiences from one another (Shaheen & Pradhan, 2019). Participants in this research were selected based on table 2-highlighted prerequisite criteria. The criterion is crucial for ensuring that a broad spectrum of diverse birthplace settings and experiences are considered to achieve the research objective comprehensively.

Table 3. Participants Selection Criteria

Criterion	Description
Age	20 - 37 Years
Location	Greater Kuala Lumpur (GKL) Area
Birthplace Setting	- Birth at Government hospitals only - Birth at Private hospitals only - Birth at both Government and private hospitals
Birthplace Experiences (Outcome)	- Positive birth experiences - Negative birth experiences
No of Childbirth	Multiparous Muslim Millennial moms (gave birth more than once)
Income Class (Level)	Middle-Income

Moreover, this research involved six experiences of Muslim millennial moms. The sample size of this research is deemed sufficient given the notion of phenomenological research inquiry. Creswell & Poth (2016) highlighted that the sample size for phenomenological research is between 5-25 participants, yet it depends on the study objectives and data saturation. Galvin (2015) and Guest et al. (2006) reviewed and statistically analyzed numerous qualitative research and discovered that the theme (data saturation) emerged among samples with six participants. For this research, data saturation emerged in Participant no 4, and the response given throughout the in-depth interview session was similar to that of others. Still, the researchers continued the data collection until the six participants, where no new information, data, or patterns emerged.

2.2 Data Analysis

The in-depth interview was transcribed verbatim and analyzed using Colaizzi's descriptive phenomenology analysis. The codes and themes were generated using seven stages of Colaizzi's descriptive analysis and validated using members' checking techniques. Members checking required the researcher to revert the analyzed transcripts to participants for validation to determine whether the information truthfully reflects the participants' meaning of the phenomenon (Candela, 2019). Participants must correct (if necessary) or add pertinent information to the research findings as part of the members' check. Additionally, each participant and birthplace (hospital) are given a pseudonym as part of the ethical research conduct, ensuring the privacy and confidentiality of each.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Participants Profiles

Table 4. Participants' Profile

Name	Age	No of Children	Birthplace Setting	Birthplace Experiences
Fifi	29	2	Both Government Hospital	Positive (satisfied) birthplace experiences
Wawa	29	2	Both Government Hospital	Positive (satisfied) birthplace experiences
Lailer	32	2	- 1 st Child (Gov. Hospital) - 2 nd Child (Private Hospital)	- 1 st Child: Traumatic - 2 nd Child: Pleasant/positive
Fazura	30	2	-1 st Child (Private Hospital) 2 nd Child (Gov. Hospital)	- 1 st Child: Dissatisfied - 2 nd Child: Pleasant/positive
Ena	32	3	All at Private Hospitals	All were pleasant/satisfied
Maryam	32	2	All at Private Hospitals	All were pleasant/satisfied

All participants indicated that when deciding on birthplace, they perceived that pregnancy and childbirth are not diseases. Thus, they enthusiastically viewed themselves as a consumer, not a patient, when consuming maternity services. For instance:

(Fazura)

".. childbirth is not a disease. It is a more risky activity".

".. as a consumer. Because we received the service from the hospital. We give birth. We don't see it as a disease".

3.2 Theme 1: Individual Differences

Participants indicated that their attitudes, Knowledge, and belief influence their birthplace decision-making process.

3.2.1 Attitude

Each individual wears a different hat that represents their attitudes, and we are unique and have our way of dealing with a specific situation. In the case of the millennial mom decision-making process, research findings identified two apparent attitudes demonstrated by this study's participants. Among the attitudes identified in this research are the laidback or casual and meticulous decision-maker. The attitude is not fixed. It changed accordingly in response to the situation and condition of the millennial mom's decision-making process.

In laidback or casual decision attitudes, participants demonstrated calmness while carrying out the birthplace decision-making process, following the process's flow and not being too detailed in their decision-making. This type of attitude can be seen in the first or subsequent birthplace decision-making process, depending on each participant's birth condition and situation. For example, Fifi mentioned that for her birthplace's decision-making process, she has no specific standard for her birthplace decisions. She preferred to follow the flow and didn't have a detailed decision plan for both of her childbirth experiences:

(Fifi)

"... I'm the types that just follow the flow".

".. I decided by the time of childbirth, before that, I was like, oh my GOD, we don't have the experience. At the time of pregnancy, it was an unplanned pregnancy, so, I just follow the flow, something like that, okay, early pregnancy needs to do a check-up, then I just go for a check-up".

On the other hand, for meticulous decision attitudes, opposite to Fifi's attitudes during her birthplace decision-making process, participants who demonstrated meticulous attitudes executed their decision-making process in detail. A prior birth experience triggers the attitudes, or it is due to a lack of experience. Take Lailer's case as an example. She went from a laid-back attitude decision-maker into a meticulous decision attitude. A traumatic previous birth experience changes her attitude drastically as she needs to ensure that the same experience won't happen again.

3.2.2 Knowledge

Information, familiarity, and skill from previous experiences determined the millennial mom's birthplace decision. Inexperienced participants demonstrated a lack of awareness of specific aspects of the birthplace decision-making process. They were unfamiliar with the process, making participants initiate several actions to assist them in the birthplace decision-making process. As per the discussion on consumer continuum involvement, participants with a low level of Knowledge tend to be involved in a high number of decision stages/cycles than informed participants.

For instance, the Wawa birthplace decision process varied between the first and second childbirth. Inexperience and lack of Knowledge about the birthplace setting caused high involvement and many decision cycles. However, knowledge gains from prior experience expedite their second-birthplace decision-making process with a smaller number of decisions cycles:

(Wawa)

".. for my second child, I don't search for anything. I just totally go for AP Hospital. Because my first experience was okay, praise to Allah, so for number two, I don't give a long thought about it, so, just go and give birth at AP Hospital".

The exact process is applied when participants experience bad service. They have to search for more info and consider the event that occurred in their previous birthplace experience as Knowledge for their future reference.

3.2.3 Belief

Positive birthplace experiences motivate future decisions and help avoid repeating the same mistake. Their belief governs the outcomes of participants' actions, reactions, feelings, and thoughts. For example, Lailer is aware of the bad reputation of the government hospital. She disregards it and chooses to believe that despite the bad review, there is still a chance for her to get fair treatment during her childbirth at that particular hospital:

(Lailer)

".. I do feel afraid because of the bad review. Still, because I believe I'm confident that 75% stated okay, they said that things only happen if the number of patients, the number of people who want to give birth is exceeded, and the patient is more than the facility. So, I believe that In sha Allah, I don't know, it is like my own instinct told that in sha Allah I would get it, means during my time I want to give birth it will not be too crowded".

On top of that, religious belief is one of the influences affecting millennial moms' birthplace decision-making process. The need to comply with religious beliefs and practices shapes millennial moms' birthplace preferences. To illustrate the statement, Ena mentioned how she looked for a

birthplace that emphasized Islamic practice as part of their service delivery. She cautiously evaluates all the available birthplace alternatives and chooses the one that complies with her religious belief:

(Ena)

".. I surveyed for a female doctor, Muslim female doctor, that is how my selection method. I choose Islamic hospital that has female doctor".

3.3 Themes 2: External Environment

Environmental influences identified in this study consisted of influences from family, friends, and social media. Participants regularly mentioned how family, friends, and social media affect their birthplace decision-making process throughout the decision-making process. The most apparent influences detected are during the information search and decision stage.

3.3.1 Family

Participants in this study mentioned that family is one of the information sources for their birthplace's decision-making process. To some, their mother's birth experience helped with their birthplace selection. Fazura said they often referred to their mother's birth experiences when looking for a birthplace option. For her, she trusted her own mother's experiences more than anything else. Fazura follow the suggestion given by their mother to go to a particular hospital with specific doctor supervision:

(Fazura)

".. We decided to go for ANR, a private hospital, because of advice from my own mother, because my mother has given birth there with Doctor KM".

3.3.2 Friends

Adhere to millennial generation characteristics, and Muslim millennial mom trusts their circle of friends the most. For the birthplace decision-making process, they mentioned that their friends' birth experiences and review influenced their birthplace decision-making process.

(Lailer)

".. I have friends that give birth. Most of my friends give birth at a government hospital. So, I heard them giving a good review of a government hospital, so I decided to give birth at a government hospital".

3.3.3 Internet and Social Media

"Google is Millennial Mom Doctor"

As part of a digital-savvy generation, the internet and social media are inevitable from being part of millennial mom decision-making. Findings indicated that social media served as a valuable information source for millennial moms. According to the participants' responses, social media does help them with the birthplace decision-making process for birthplace. The words Google is countless mentioned by all participants during the interview sessions. It is the verb in their birthplace's decision-making process. In her interview transcripts, Fifi mentioned that social media significantly influenced the birthplace decision. She trusted the information posted and shared all over the internet and social media:

(Fifi)

"... most frequent, most referred is social media".

".. I absolutely 100% relied on Google, Internet, Facebook, and social media".

Moreover, participants mentioned how viral news and the current trend of birthplace practices shared worldwide and on social media swayed their birthplace decision even though they had made up their minds. As Wawa shared in her interview, she had a last-minute intention to switch to another hospital because she read about the viral news of other bad experiences at the same hospital where she chose to give birth. Adding to this, a trend like giving birth at Andorra Women's Hospital is another sensational topic frequently shared on social media. Stories, experiences, and video pictures shared by other cybernauts on social media platforms ignited participants' intentions to try the Andorra services. Wawa said that she had the desire to go to Andorra Hospital because of the facility that they have captured her attention:

(Wawa)

".. I want to go to AND. because I want to try, I don't know, maybe because the building is beautiful".

Considering everything, you can see how easily social media influenced the millennial mom's decision-making process. A couple of beautiful shots, a panoramic video, and a catchy caption enough to persuade others influenced their decision-making process. In sum, from the interview with all millennial mom participants, a few things that can be learned throughout the entire decision stage are that mothers do not necessarily complete the decision stage before moving up to another. With experience and Knowledge, some stages may not be relevant to be repeated for subsequent birthplace decision-making. Furthermore, the involvement level in the birthplace decision-making process varied according to the birth condition and situation. Ultimately, this research's findings corresponded to the participants' stand, which is the birthplace decision-making process is unique and dissimilar from any other service decision-making process.

4. DISCUSSION

Throughout the childbearing journey, Muslim millennial moms described their close social circle (e.g., family, friends) and internet social media as influential and significant sources that guided their birthplace selection, particularly during their first-time pregnancy journey. Past research (i.e., Cabeza-Ramírez et al., 2022) profoundly agreed that family, friends, and the internet (Pop et al., 2021) are essential and influential decision influences, especially for high-involvement product consumption. Moreover, regarding individual differences, López-Toribio et al., (2021) uncovered in their studies that attitudes toward childbirth significantly influence and determine young mothers' childbirth and birthplace decisions.

Meanwhile, Busalim et al. (2022) explained that attitudes and Knowledge are interrelated, shaping consumer behavior and action toward particular matters. Knowledge served as a data bank, assisting mothers in making birthplace decisions. Wigert et al. (2020) further elaborated that mother built up their understanding and Knowledge about childbirth from their social environment, where the Knowledge gained helps them practically sort out childbirth-related decisions. Furthermore, millennial moms stated that their beliefs are grounded by religion and faith in deciding where to have their babies. They considered a birthplace that is Syariah compliance. Muslichah et al. (2019) and Iqbal and Nisha's (2016) findings paralleled the millennial moms' acts, and their research confirmed that religion served as informative guidelines that influence consumer purchase decisions.

5. CONCLUSION

Overall, it can be concluded that the EBM consumer decision-making model reflected the Muslim millennial mom's decision-making process relevantly. To better understand how Muslim millennial moms choose their birthplace, the researcher expanded on existing Knowledge by extemporizing existing decision stages tailored to their birthplace decision-making process. Prior research on the birthplace decision-making process has been profoundly examined through the lenses of medical and health points of view, positioning the mothers as the patient rather than the consumer. Therefore, this study shed light on understanding the variables that influence the decision process from the consumer's perspective as low-risk (normal) childbirth in which being pregnant was a choice, not a disease, and giving birth is a must thing do, not an option. Also, regarding theoretical debate, the existing EBM model is deemed relevant and comprehensive to understanding consumer purchase decisions. Research on Muslim millennial moms' variables influencing the consumer decision-making process uncovered that the grand model of consumer behavior is adaptable and relevant to understanding service product consumption. Still, it requires modification by incorporating elements of emotion, experience, and involvement continuum as part of the consumer decision-making process model to examine and understand the phenomenon under observation holistically.

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